

The influence of cut edge heterogeneity in complex phase steel sheet edge cracking: An experimental and numerical investigation

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated how geometrical variations along the perimeter of sheared edges influenced the formability of advanced high-strength steel sheets during hole expansion. A combined numerical and experimental approach was employed, based on the standardised ISO 16630 Hole Expansion Test. The shear cutting process prior to cut edge forming was modelled using the Particle Finite Element Method, which enabled accurate prediction of edge morphology and deformation within the shear affected zone. The resulting geometries and residual fields were transferred to three-dimensional blank meshes for hole expansion simulations. A cold-rolled complex-phase steel was used, processed with varying cutting clearances to produce distinct edge conditions. Circumferential heterogeneities, including burr-to-no-burr transitions and irregular burnish patterns, were shown to significantly reduce edge formability and promote early crack initiation. These effects were found to be more detrimental than damage distributed through the thickness of the sheared edge. To represent such irregularities in numerical modelling, a hybrid meshing strategy was introduced, incorporating three-dimensional microscopy data into the simulation workflow. This approach improved the accuracy of predicted hole expansion ratios and allowed reproduction of experimentally observed fracture patterns. Stress analysis showed that geometric imperfections around the hole perimeter elevated local stress triaxiality and accelerated damage development. The findings emphasised the importance of achieving uniform cut edge quality to ensure reliable forming performance and reduce the risk of edge cracking during manufacturing.

1. Introduction

Advanced high strength steels (AHSS) have become increasingly important in the automotive industry due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, enabling vehicle lightweighting without compromising structural integrity. This is especially beneficial for sheet metal components, where down-gauging achieves substantial weight reduction. However, the shear cutting process performed before cold forming operations introduces sheared edge damage, which significantly reduces the formability of the cut edge. This reduction in formability is caused by edge cracking, a manufacturing issue where sheared edges are prone to failure before necking and well below the limits predicted by conventional forming limit curves. Therefore, understanding the mechanical behaviour of AHSS in response to edge damage is essential for optimising manufacturing processes and preventing component failures.

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Fig. 1. A schematic cross section image of the final cut edge morphology, showing the through-thickness characteristic features and surfaces generally created during the shear cutting process.

The edge cracking phenomenon has been thoroughly investigated over the past few decades, with considerable experimental efforts aimed at defining the critical factors of the sheared edge damage. An early study by Konieczny and Henderson [1] identified poor edge preparation and inappropriate cutting clearance as key contributors to stress concentrations, which in turn led to premature failure through edge cracking. Subsequent work by Shih et al. [2] demonstrated that micro-cracks induced during the shearing process served as initiation sites for fractures, highlighting the importance of achieving smooth and uniform cut edges. Further investigations by Dykeman et al. [3] and Thomas [4] emphasised the role of work hardening and microstructural damage in the shear affected zone (SAZ) in reducing ductility, thus increasing the risk of edge cracking. A schematic representation of the SAZ is shown in Fig. 1, which also illustrates its characteristic cut edge morphology, including the rollover, burnish, fracture surface, and burr.

Experimental investigations have been invaluable in identifying the critical factors contributing to edge cracking. However, numerical modelling of the shear cutting process and subsequent forming offers additional detailed insights into this phenomenon. The controlled and repeatable nature of numerical modelling also facilitates material and process optimisation. Several key studies have advanced the application of numerical modelling to better understand edge cracking, each addressing different aspects of sheared edge damage. Regarding shear cutting simulation, this field has evolved significantly over the past decades, from early macroscopic stress and strain predictions, as demonstrated by Goijaerts et al. [5], to more advanced methods that account for material fracture, such as the work by Hambli and Potiron [6], Klingenberg and Singh [7] and Dalloz et al. [8]. In the publications by Thipprakmas et al. [9] and Bacha et al. [10], adaptive re-meshing and Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) formulations was applied for improved numerical accuracy when handling the extensive deformations of the shearing process, enabling predictions of surface imperfections and crack propagation paths in various materials. More recent efforts have focused on addressing the specific challenges of AHSS, with Canales et al. [11] incorporating strain-rate sensitivity and Gutknecht et al. [12] and Zhang et al. [13] developing advanced constitutive models for enhanced predictive precision.

While the combination of adaptive re-meshing and ALE formulations represents the state-of-the-art for shear cutting simulations, ALE faces limitations in handling extreme and unpredictable deformations, as reported by Cremonesi et al. [14]. Besides this constraint, re-meshing schemes can introduce result diffusion and smoothing, reducing the accuracy of localised residual predictions along the sheared edge and within the shear affected zone. Given these modelling challenges, the present work applies the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) as an alternative for shear cutting simulations. PFEM is an emerging numerical method for large deformation solid mechanics, offering both high numerical accuracy and computational efficiency. It combines the efficiency of the Finite Element Method (FEM) with the numerical stability of particle methods under large deformations by treating particles of the analysis domain as nodes in a FE-mesh and solving the governing equations using standard FEM formulations. To prevent mesh distortion, the FE-mesh undergoes continuous particle re-connectivity throughout the simulation. In the context of shear cutting, PFEM ensures appropriate element aspect ratios during extreme shearing deformation while enabling the creation of new surfaces in the fracture process. Its predictive accuracy and ability to preserve results were demonstrated by Sandin et al. [15], who developed an axisymmetric PFEM framework with ductile damage implementation for shear cutting simulations of high strength steel. Although the axisymmetric PFEM model demonstrates high predictive capabilities, 3D PFEM modelling is under development to expand future investigation possibilities.

Extending the scope beyond shear cutting simulations, two-step cutting and forming simulations enables a deeper understanding of how shear cutting influences subsequent manufacturing defects. For example, this was demonstrated by Butcher et al. [16] who showed that sheared edge damage plays a crucial role in edge cracking through hole expansion simulations, highlighting the importance of accounting for localised SAZ damage in predictive models. Similarly, Wang et al. [17] employed the now

Nomenclature

A_{80}	Total elongation
AHSS	Advanced High-Strength Steel
ALE	Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian formulation
CP1000HD	Cold-rolled complex-phase steel with an ultimate tensile strength of 1000 MPa
C_1, C_2, C_3	Modified Mohr-Columb failure locus parameters
$Cl.$	Cutting clearance
D	Damage parameter in the GISSMO model
D_c	Critical damage parameter
D_h	Average hole diameter at the first through-thickness crack in hole expansion test
$D_{h,outer}$	Outer edge hole diameter at the first through-thickness crack in hole expansion test
D_0	Initial hole diameter in hole expansion test
d_{Die}	Die diameter in shear cutting
d_{Punch}	Punch diameter in shear cutting
$f(\sigma)$	Anisotropic yield function
F	Instability parameter in the GISSMO model
F, G, H, L, M, N	Hill 48 model parameters
FEM	Finite Element Method
GISSMO	Generalized Incremental Stress State-dependent damage Model
HER	Hole Expansion Ratio
HET	Hole Expansion Test
Hill 48	Orthotropic plasticity model
ISO 16630	ISO standard for steel sheet hole expansion test
MMC	Modified Mohr-Coulomb
m	Degradation rate in the GISSMO model
n	Damage accumulation rate in the GISSMO model
n_{Ag}	Strain hardening exponent at uniform elongation
p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4	El-Magd plasticity model parameters
PFEM	Particle Finite Element Method
RD	Rolling direction
r_4	Lankford coefficient at 4% elongation
r_0, r_{45}, r_{90}	Lankford coefficients at 0°, 45° and 90° to the rolling direction
s	Deviatoric stress tensor
SAZ	shear affected zone
t_{Blank}	Blank thickness
TD	Transverse direction
UE	Uniform elongation
UTS	Ultimate tensile strength
YS	Yield strength
$\varepsilon_i(\eta)$	Stress-state dependent instability strain
$\varepsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$	Stress-state dependent equivalent plastic strain at failure
$\dot{\varepsilon}_p$	Plastic strain increment
η	Stress triaxiality
$\bar{\theta}$	Normalised Lode angle parameter
μ	Static friction coefficient
μ_d	Dynamic friction coefficient
σ	Cauchy stress tensor
$\bar{\sigma}$	Effective stress
σ_0	Yield stress at 0° to the rolling direction
σ_{Nom}	Nominal stress tensor
σ_{vM}	von Mises stress
$\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$	Cauchy normal stress components
$\tau_{xy}, \tau_{yz}, \tau_{zx}$	Cauchy shear stress components

well-established Modified Mohr–Coulomb (MMC) model in two-stage cutting and extrusion simulations, demonstrating that cutting-induced damage and plastic deformation are the primary factors reducing stretch-flangeability. Among the MMC criterion, several advanced ductile damage models have been developed to improve the prediction of shear-induced damage and subsequent edge failure. Among these, the Hybrid Damage Model (HDM), originally proposed by Lian et al. [18] and applied in the work of Li et al.

[19], has been shown to effectively capture failure initiation at sheared edges. Similarly, the Hosford-Coulomb model, introduced by Mohr and Marcadet [20] and later employed by Basak et al. [21], has demonstrated strong predictive capabilities in modelling trimmed edge profiles and burr formation. Additionally, variations of the Lemaitre model, as explored in studies by Cao et al. [22] and Yue et al. [23], further highlight ongoing efforts to refine ductile failure predictions by considering microstructural influences. Building on these advancements, Li et al. [24] introduced a ductile fracture model that explicitly accounts for pre-damage accumulation from the blanking process, addressing the critical role of prior shearing-induced damage in subsequent edge cracking. In addition, Li et al. [19] emphasised the significance of material anisotropy in predicting edge fracture in dual-phase steel. Their models showed that anisotropy-induced localisation is a key factor in edge cracking during hole expansion, underscoring the need to account for anisotropy in predictive models to accurately capture the material's failure behaviour. Beyond the continuum mechanics framework, Zhang et al. [25] applied microstructural modelling of shear cutting and subsequent forming to establish links between microstructural features and edge cracking. Their work aimed to optimise microstructure for enhanced sheared edge formability. Similarly, Han et al. [26] investigated the sheared edge damage in DP780 steel and highlighted that microvoids formed at phase interfaces and inclusions significantly influence crack initiation, reinforcing the importance of microstructural characterisation for understanding sheared edge failure. Consistent with this micromechanical perspective, Habibi et al. [27] concluded that more homogeneous microstructures in steel materials significantly improve sheared edge formability.

Despite the predictive accuracy and numerical advancements presented in the publications mentioned, the focus is almost exclusively placed on through-thickness sheared edge damage. While the through-thickness damage induced by shear cutting undoubtedly plays a critical role in reducing the stretch-flangeability of AHSS grades, much of the existing literature in this field tends to overlook the influence of peripheral heterogeneity along the cut edge. Notably, this aspect was addressed by Qian et al. [28], who observed circumferential surface irregularities generated during the shear cutting process which furthermore acted as initiation sites for edge cracks in subsequent hole flanging operations. Through the use of an anisotropic material representation and ductile damage modelling, their 3D two-step HET simulation could reproduce irregular cut edge patterns along the hole perimeter where complex, high-triaxiality stress-states accelerated the damage accumulation and induced edge cracks.

Building on this foundation, the present article seeks to further explore the effects of circumferentially heterogeneous morphologies along the cut edge in more detail. It aims to assess the negative influence of these heterogeneous conditions on stretch-flangeability and compare their significance to the conventionally prioritised through-thickness SAZ damage. This study presents numerical and experimental analyses of the two-stage cutting and forming ISO 16630 Hole Expansion Test (HET) [29], which is the only standardised method for assessing sheared edge formability. The investigation begins with numerical shear cutting modelling using the PFEM scheme developed by Sandin et al. [15]. To bridge the gap between 2D and 3D modelling, a high-resolution 2D-to-3D mapping scheme is implemented, similar to the approach proposed by Hu et al. [30], but with significantly finer discretisation. This scheme enabled 3D hole expansion modelling, performed for edge cracking analysis with residual sheared edge results and validated against experimental results to evaluate its predictive accuracy. This combined numerical and experimental approach enables in-depth studies of edge cracking mechanisms and the influence of circumferential cut edge heterogeneity on the sheared edge formability. Beyond its scientific contribution, this work addresses practical challenges in industrial forming, where edge cracking remains an issue. Factors such as tool alignment, clearance consistency, and the formation of micro-notches around the cut edge perimeter are often difficult to control, but can detrimentally affect edge forming properties. A more detailed understanding of these influences can support improved tool setup, maintenance routines, and process optimisation. By integrating realistic edge characterisation with predictive modelling, this study seeks to provide insights directly applicable to industrial practice.

2. Experimental methods

The experimental methods of the present work consisted in material characterisation utilised in the numerical model and the two-stage ISO 16630 Hole Expansion Test for edge crack assessment. This section will provide the necessary background for reproducing the experimental work.

2.1. Material characterisation

In this study, a 1.5 mm CR700Y980T-CH automotive steel sheet was examined in its cold-rolled, pickled, and continuously annealed state. Hereafter, this material will be referred to as CP1000HD. CP1000HD is a high-ductility, cold-rolled complex phase steel with an ultimate tensile strength of 1000 MPa, making it suitable for automotive applications such as crash management systems and structural components. Its fine-grained microstructure comprises homogeneous bainite, martensite, and retained austenite. The tensile properties of the CP1000HD grade from ISO 6892-1 [31] tensile tests are shown in Table 1.

For calibrating the constitutive models used in shear cutting and hole expansion simulations (detailed in Section 3.1), the material's plastic hardening behaviour was determined through hydraulic bulge testing in accordance with ISO 16808 [32], while its anisotropic response was obtained using the tensile properties listed in Table 1.

The stress-state-dependent failure and instability strain measures, $\varepsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$ and $\varepsilon_i(\eta)$, were calibrated using the methodology proposed by Marth et al. [33]. These values are essential for the ductile damage and failure modelling scheme, further detailed in Section 3.1. The calibration method involved using three tensile specimens specifically designed to deform and fail under designated stress states. The tensile specimen and designated stress-state at failure are shown in Fig. 2. The strain fields of the tensile specimens were measured until failure using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) with a 0.1 mm facet grid and 75% facet overlap. The Stepwise Modelling Method (SMM), presented by Marth et al. [33], was then employed on specimen (a) to (c) to determine the experimental

Table 1

Tensile properties in different material directions relative to the rolling direction (RD) for CP1000HD with a thickness of $t_{Blank} = 1.5$ mm, yield strength (YS), tensile strength (UTS), uniform elongation (UE), total elongation ($A80$), n -value at uniform elongation (nAg) and r -value determined at 4% elongation ($r4$).

RD	YS [MPa]	UTS [MPa]	UE [%]	$A80$ [%]	nAg [-]	$r4$ [-]
0°	893	1052	7.3	11.1	0.071	0.91
45°	905	1052	7.0	10.6	0.068	1.02
90°	909	1062	7.1	10.7	0.068	0.96

Fig. 2. The tensile specimen used for determining $\epsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$, showing in (a) the shear specimen corresponding to deformation and failure at $\eta \approx 0$, (b) the R15 specimen at $\eta \approx 0.5$ and (c) the R3.75 specimen at $\eta \approx 0.6$.

equivalent failure strain for each specimen and its corresponding stress state, utilising the DIC strain field data. SMM calculated the specimen's stress tensor along a localisation path across the specimen width for each DIC frame. By applying the Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, and yield strength, SMM could obtain the effective plastic strain and corresponding stress triaxiality at the point of specimen failure, considering through thickness strain by the constant volume constraint. For the R15 and R3.75 specimens, the failure strain used for failure locus calibration was determined by extrapolating the surface failure strain values through the thickness, based on finite element results of the strain gradient. To validate this assumption, the same tensile specimens were modelled using the calibrated damage model, which reproduced accurate force versus displacement results as shown in Fig. 3. This procedure was not necessary for the shear specimen as this did not undergo any cross section thinning. The tensile experiments were conducted transversal to the rolling direction in order to obtain conservative failure strain values.

2.2. Sheet punching

Close-cut sheet punching experiments with a wide range of cutting clearances were conducted as the first part of the two-stage ISO 16630 HET. The cutting clearance defines the intentional horizontal gap between punch and die as a percentage of the material thickness, according to Eq. (1). Varying the cutting clearances was done by using dies with different diameters, while keeping the punch diameter and the blank thickness constant.

$$\text{Clearance [\%]} = \frac{d_{\text{Die}} - d_{\text{Punch}}}{2t_{\text{Blank}}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Table 2 states the clearances and corresponding die diameter used for the sheet punching experiments. The clearances were chosen to address specific punching scenarios. For low cutting clearances, formation of secondary burnish was achieved. This was shown by Larour et al. [34] to drastically reduce edge formability. The intermediate 12.1% cutting clearance was chosen as it is generally considered optimal for stretch-flangeability and was demonstrated by Larour et al. [34] to enhance cut edge forming limits for the AHSS grade investigated in this study. In contrast, the 40.3% cutting clearance case was selected to challenge the modelling capabilities and induce substantial plastic deformation and burr formation, despite being impractical for industrial applications. The case of 27.0% cutting clearance caused partial burr formation, thus serves as a rare, but critical case regarding cut edge formability. For all punching experiments, the blank thickness (1.5 mm) and the punch diameter (9.998 mm) remained constant. Sharp tools with edge radii of 30 μm were used and no significant tool edge wear was assumed to occur during the experimental work. The

Fig. 3. Validation of the calibrated damage model by simulating the tensile specimen used in the calibration process, where the solid lines show the simulation results and the dashed lines show the experiments.

Table 2

The geometric hole punching parameters used in experiments for clearances (Cl.) 5.3–40.3%, where d_{Die} is the die diameter. In the experiments, the punch diameter d_p was constant at 9.998 mm and the blank thickness was $t = 1.5$ mm.

Cl. [%]	5.3	12.1	27.0	40.3
d_{Die} [mm]	10.16	10.36	10.81	11.21

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. (a) Servo-hydraulic clinching machine used for experimental hole punching. (b) Schematic representation of the hole punching configuration, illustrating the cutting clearance, tool placement and the axial symmetry line.

experimental sheet punching was performed using a servo-hydraulic clinching machine with 150 kN maximum load. The blank was clamped with 5–15 kN before punching. Punching speed of 0.05 mm/s was used for resembling quasi-static condition, thus minimising dynamic- and strain rate effects and adiabatic heating as proposed by the ISO 16630 HET standard. Fig. 4 displays the servo-hydraulic clinching machine used for experimental hole punching, while (b) provides a schematic representation of the hole punching configuration, highlighting the cutting clearance, tool placement and the axial symmetry line of the hole.

2.3. Hole expansion test

To assess the sheared edge formability, the Hole Expansion Ratio (HER) of punched holes with varying clearances was determined. The HER measurements followed the ISO 16630 standard, using a $60^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ conical punch and a burr-up condition, as this represents the worst-case scenario for HER values. According to the ISO standard, the experiments were manually stopped

Fig. 5. Experimental HET machine in (a), showing the blank holder and the conical punch and the HET specimen placement. In (b) is a schematic setup for the ISO 16630 test with burr up condition.

upon observing the first visual through-thickness crack. At this point, the HER was calculated using Eq. (2), where D_h is the average hole diameter at the first through-thickness crack and D_0 is the initial hole diameter.

The hole expansion test was conducted on punched holes produced by all cutting clearances listed in Table 2, along with a drilled hole expansion test to obtain a reference HER value from an undamaged cut edge. The two-stage ISO 16630 hole expansion test was selected for this investigation due to its simplicity and efficiency in handling large test series. The tests were performed using the same punching and testing machines, with the same operator, in the same laboratory, and with consistent punching and expansion parameters. To minimise scattering, punching and testing were completed within a maximum of 15 min, as additional delays can significantly reduce HER levels and increase variability. The absolute standard deviation of HER values ranged from 5%–10%, which is low enough to demonstrate significant material-related HER variations in relation to punch parameters beyond stochastic scattering, with three replicates. Fig. 5 presents the experimental HET machine along with the schematic setup for the ISO 16630 test. For the current tests, the HET die radius (R_{Die}) was set to 5 mm in accordance with the ISO standard, while the die hole diameter was $D_{Die} = 62.5$ mm.

$$HER [\%] = \frac{D_h - D_0}{D_0} \cdot 100 \tag{2}$$

3. Numerical modelling

The following section describes the numerical modelling of the sheet punching and subsequent hole expansion simulations, including constitutive modelling and numerical setup.

3.1. Constitutive modelling

In the current work, the Hill 48 orthotropic plasticity model by Hill [35] combined with the El-Magd isotropic plasticity hardening law proposed by El-magd et al. [36] were used in numerical models to describe the material deformation behaviour. The results from hydraulic bulge testing and uniaxial tensile testing, presented in Section 2.1, were utilised for the calibration of the plasticity models, where Eq. (3) states the Hill 48 yield function and Eq. (4) gives the El-Magd plastic hardening function.

The calibration of Hill48 plasticity parameters in this work is based on experimentally measured r-values, as they provide a direct representation of the material’s anisotropic plastic response. This approach is particularly suitable for capturing the directional resistance to thinning, which is crucial for accurately predicting strain localisation and formability in edge deformation processes. However, as noted by Mu et al. [37], using r-values has limitations, as the Hill 48 model assumes specific distributions of yield stress and r-values that may not fully capture complex anisotropic behaviour. Despite this, r-values are widely used in sheet metal forming studies, and given the limited anisotropic behaviour of CP1000HD, the influence of these limitations on the present modelling is expected to be minimal.

$$f(\sigma) = \sqrt{F(\sigma_Y - \sigma_Z)^2 + G(\sigma_Z - \sigma_X)^2 + H(\sigma_X - \sigma_Y)^2 + 2L\tau_{yz}^2 + 2M\tau_{zx}^2 + 2N\tau_{xy}^2} \tag{3}$$

$$\bar{\sigma} = p_1 + p_2 \cdot \epsilon_p + p_3 \cdot (1 - e^{-p_4 \cdot \epsilon_p}) \tag{4}$$

Table 3
Plasticity model parameters p_1 to p_4 .

p_1 [MPa]	p_2 [MPa]	p_3 [MPa]	p_4
910	297	229	31.1

Table 4
Lankford ratios r_0, r_{45}, r_{90} and the Hill 48 yield locus parameters.

r_0	r_{45}	r_{90}	F	G	H	L	M	N
0.91	1.02	0.96	0.50	0.52	0.48	1.50	1.50	1.55

Fig. 6. The calibrated Hill 48 yield locus compared to the von Mises yield locus expressed in 2D principal stress space. The figure axes are normalised in RD 0° and RD 90° directions with respect to the yield stress. (a) shows the full locus, while (b) shows a magnified view.

The parameters p_1 to p_4 of Eq. (4) were determined using a least-square fitting against the experimental data, expressed as equivalent plastic strain versus effective stress. Table 3 states the fitted parameters p_1 to p_4 of the CP1000HD El-Magd strain hardening model.

As displayed by Table 1, the CP1000HD showed limited anisotropic behaviour. This statement is further emphasised by the calibrated Hill 48 parameters presented in Table 4 and the comparison between the calibrated Hill 48 yield locus and the corresponding von Mises locus in Fig. 6. Despite the material’s near-isotropic response, the Hill 48 model is employed to account for any subtle anisotropic effects that may still influence the mechanical behaviour under specific loading conditions. The Hill 48 parameters F, G, H, N were determined using r-values according to the work by Basak et al. [38] using the relationships in Eq. (5), where parameters L, M are per default 1.5.

$$\begin{aligned}
 H &= r_0 / (1 + r_0) \\
 G &= 1 / (1 + r_0) \\
 F &= H / r_{90}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

$$N = (r_0 + r_{90})(1 + 2r_{45}) / (2r_{90}(1 + r_0))$$

For modelling of damage- and failure during the hole expansion simulation, the Generalized Incremental Stress State dependant damage Model (GISSMO) by Neukamm et al. [39] was used. The GISSMO model accumulated a damage parameter D according to Eq. (6). In this equation, n represents the accumulation rate, $\epsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$ denotes the stress-state dependent failure strain values, and ϵ_p is the plastic strain increment. The stress-state variables η and $\bar{\theta}$ are the stress triaxiality and the normalised Lode angle parameter, respectively, as defined in Eqs. (7) and (8). Here, σ is the Cauchy stress tensor and \mathbf{s} is the deviatoric stress tensor.

$$\dot{D} = \frac{n}{\epsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta})} D^{(1-\frac{1}{n})} \dot{\epsilon}_p \tag{6}$$

$$\eta = \frac{\text{tr}(\sigma)}{3\sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \mathbf{s} : \mathbf{s}} \tag{7}$$

Table 5
Dimensionless MMC parameters C_1 to C_3 .

C_1	C_2	C_3
0.4073	1.5960	1.1205

$$\bar{\theta} = \frac{1}{3} \arccos \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3} \det(\mathbf{s})}{2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{s} : \mathbf{s} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \quad (8)$$

Similarly to the damage parameter, the instability parameter F accumulated according to Eq. (9). In this equation, $\varepsilon_i(\eta)$ defines the strain values at which material degradation initiates.

$$\dot{F} = \frac{n}{\varepsilon_i(\eta)} F^{(1-\frac{1}{n})} \dot{\varepsilon}_p \quad (9)$$

When $F = 1$, material degradation was enabled, representing the reduction of the material's load bearing capacity due to void growth and coalescence. In the GISSMO model, this was represented by influencing the effective stress tensor $\bar{\sigma}$ via Eq. (10). Here, the nominal stress tensor $\bar{\sigma}_{\text{Nom.}}$ was affected by the accumulated damage parameter D and the critical damage parameter D_c , which was reached when $F = 1$. The parameter m denotes the degradation rate.

$$\bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma}_{\text{Nom.}} \left(1 - \left(\frac{D - D_c}{1 - D_c} \right)^m \right) \quad (10)$$

The stress-state-dependent strain measures $\varepsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$ and $\varepsilon_i(\eta)$, found in Eqs. (6) and (9) respectively, were experimentally determined. This was accomplished using the tensile testing procedure detailed in Section 2.1 using the tensile specimen shown in Fig. 2. The tensile specimens were specifically designed to deform and fail under predefined stress states, with $\varepsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta})$ measured at specimen failure and $\varepsilon_i(\eta)$ obtained at peak tensile load. Commonly, an additional hole tensile specimen is used in this testing scheme for measuring failure strain at uniaxial tension. However, this sample specimen is known to imply difficulties in DIC measurement at the hole edge, as shown by Wang [40]. In addition, the current study experienced failure inside the specimen due to the high material ductility, a discrepancy also reported by Anderson et al. [41] and Lou and Huh [42]. Instead, the equivalent failure strain value at uniaxial tension was determined from HET experiments with drilled, undamaged holes according to the work by Butcher et al. [16] and Pathak et al. [43]. This procedure utilises a hole expansion test, where the outer hole edge deforms constantly in uniaxial tension and remains unaffected by punch contact throughout the test until failure. By measurement of the outer edge hole diameter at fracture $D_{h,\text{outer}}$, the equivalent failure strain for uniaxial tension ε_{eq}^f is expressed in Eq. (11), in a simplified manner by Butcher et al. [44].

$$\varepsilon_{eq}^f \approx \ln \left(\frac{D_{h,\text{outer}}}{D_0} \right) \quad (11)$$

The obtained failure strain values were used for calibration of the modified Mohr-Coloumb locus by Bai and Wierzbicki [45,46]. The MMC locus is given by Eq. (12) and the parameters C_1 , C_2 , C_3 were calibrated with least-squares curve fitting. Since plane stress was assumed, Eq. (13) was used for relating the stress-triaxiality η to the normalised Lode angle parameter $\bar{\theta}$. Table 5 states the calibrated MMC parameters C_1 , C_2 , C_3 . The MMC locus, along with the calibration points and deformation paths for each calibration experiment, is presented in Fig. 7, shown in (a) for plane stress conditions and (b) for the full three-dimensional failure locus.

$$\varepsilon_{eq}^f(\eta, \bar{\theta}) = \left\{ C_2 \left[\sqrt{\frac{1 + C_1^2}{3}} \cos\left(\frac{\bar{\theta}\pi}{6}\right) + C_1 \left(\eta + \frac{1}{3} \sin\left(\frac{\bar{\theta}\pi}{6}\right) \right) \right] \right\}^{-\frac{1}{C_3}} \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{\theta} = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \cos^{-1} \left(-\frac{27}{2} \eta \left(\eta^2 - \frac{1}{3} \right) \right) \quad (13)$$

In line with the findings of Bao and Wierzbicki [47] and related studies on this topic [19,48], a cut-off value of $\eta = -1/3$ was imposed on the failure locus. This constraint ensures that damage accumulation is restricted to stress states above the designated threshold.

3.2. Numerical modelling of sheet punching using PFEM

In the publications by Sandin et al. [15,49], a PFEM shear cutting model was developed for axisymmetrical shear cutting simulations of the CP1000HD material and thoroughly validated against experimental work. For the present paper, results from the work by Sandin et al. [49] are used, utilising the same PFEM scheme for simulations of sheet punching with the cutting clearances presented in Table 2, ranging from 5.3% to 40.3%. Residual results in terms of cut edge profile, damage and stress- and strain data were then extracted from the numerical results and used for hole expansion simulations, further described in Section 3.3. The work by Sandin et al. [49] provides a comprehensive description and validation of the shear cutting simulations employed in this study. For further details, readers are referred to that publication, which, for instance, presents an in-depth analysis of process forces, bulk material deformation within the shear affected zone, and cut edge morphologies across different cutting clearances. For elaborate theoretical description of the numerical sheet punching modelling, see the publication by Sandin

Fig. 7. The calibrated MMC locus obtained using the calibration procedure described in Section 2.1, shown for (a) plane stress conditions and (b) the full failure locus.

et al. [15]. Fig. 8 shows the numerical cut edge profiles from simulations using 5.3%, 12.1%, 27.0% and 40.3% cutting clearance and the corresponding experimental results extracted using non-destructive 3D microscopy at different positions around the hole perimeter. The experimental technique used to capture cut edge morphologies enables repeated analysis of the punched specimen while providing an accurate representation of the cut edge morphology at arbitrary positions along the hole perimeter. Additionally, Fig. 9 illustrates the distribution of characteristic cut edge surfaces across the blank thickness for each cutting clearance, providing a detailed comparison of the cut edge parameters.

3.3. Numerical ISO 16630 HET modelling

The hole expansion test is undoubtedly a three-dimensional problem, as edge cracks commonly forms in a manner that lacks axial symmetry. This requires a transition from the 2D PFEM axisymmetric shear cutting model to a 3D FEM hole expansion model that accounts for the complex stress and strain distribution during the sheared edge deformation. For numerical modelling of the hole expansion test, the final 2D cut edge contours from the PFEM sheet punching models were first discretised with 2D hexagonal elements of characteristic element length of 8.5–10 μm . The hexagonal 2D mesh were consecutively swept 45°, giving a solid structure. Restricting the numerical HET modelling to 1/8 of the entire blank was done to reduce the computational effort and conforms with the work by, for instance, Wang et al. [17]. Sweeping the structure with 375 steps gave circumferential element sizes of $\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$. This generated hexagonal solid elements in the SAZ with characteristic element lengths in size of 8.5–10 μm . The remaining blank structure was meshed using hexagonal elements with increasing characteristic lengths further from the SAZ, minimising computational effort while preserving high resolution in the shear affected zone. The number of elements in the 3D blank meshes, which ultimately depends on the width of the shear affected zone ranged from 217 000 to 305 000. Notably, for the 5.3% cutting clearance, where secondary burnish introduced significant detail to the cut edge surface, a high number of elements was required to ensure accurate discretisation. The simulations, executed on 64 Intel® Xeon® Gold 6248R CPU cores running at 3.0 GHz computer cluster, required approximately 128–200 CPU-hours. The transition from the 2D PFEM cut edge geometry to the 3D sheared edge blank mesh is illustrated in Fig. 10.

To the solid 3D mesh the axisymmetrical results were mapped with the stress- and strain tensor, equivalent plastic strain, von Mises stress and damage parameters related to the damage- and failure model. The damage- and failure model used in the PFEM sheet punching modelling by Sandin et al. [15] is analogous with the GISSMO model. Therefore, mapping of the residual damage results from the PFEM modelling to the 3D HET modelling was possible. A comparison between the axisymmetrical and the mapped 3D von Mises stress is shown in Fig. 11 for 12.1% cutting clearance. The drilled hole condition was modelled with a squared structured solid hexagonal blank mesh swept in the same way as the axisymmetric residual cut edge shapes.

Fig. 8. Experimental cut edge profiles (colours) and the axisymmetrical numerically predicted cut edges (black) overlaid for cutting clearances of (a) 5.3%, (b) 12.1%, (c) 27.0% and (d) 40.3%. The experimental cut edge profiles were determined at 0°, 90°, 180° and 270° around the punched hole circumference. For 27.0% cutting clearance, additional cut edge profiles were extracted for providing information at no-burr and burr sections.

Panoramic images of the experimental cut edges are shown in Fig. 12 (a,c,e,g) for 5.3%, 12.1%, 27.0% and 40.3% cutting clearance respectively. The corresponding solid blank meshes produced by the presented pre-processing method are shown in Fig. 12 (b,d,f,h). The green lines in Fig. 12 show the outer edges of the blank and the red lines enclose the burnish surfaces.

The conical punch with 60° shape was modelled with rigid hexahedral shell elements and assigned displacement in negative y -direction. The blank holder and die were also rigid. The clamping of the blank was done by fixing back end nodes in all degrees of freedom, assuming that the clamping force in experiment was large enough to prohibit motion of the blank. The axisymmetrical boundary conditions on the blank symmetry edges were done by constraining out-of-plane motion of the edge nodes. The HET simulations were performed with the LS-Dyna R14.0.0 explicit solver. The blank was assigned an assumed strain approach elements formulation (ELFORM = -2) which avoided shear locking if poor aspect ratios would occur and ensured accurate results for large element deformation. The blank material deformation behaviour was described by the LS-Dyna Hill48 material model for solid elements (material model number 122-3D) and the GISSMO damage- and failure model based on the input from Section 3.1. To the surface-to-surface mortar contact definition, further described by Borrvall [50], a static friction coefficient of $\mu_s = 0.1$ and a dynamic friction coefficient of $\mu_d = 0.15$ were assumed in the simulations in accordance to the work by Wang et al. [17], Li et al. [19] and Habibi et al. [27]. The mortar contact implementation in LS-DYNA R14.0.0 provides robust and accurate handling of sliding contact conditions, but this comes at the cost of increased computational demand compared to conventional automatic penalty-based surface-to-surface contacts. After the finished HET simulation, the HER was determined by fitting a three-point radius circle using the innermost points away from the crack, in accordance to the ISO 16630 standard.

3.3.1. Hybrid numerical HET modelling

The cut edge morphologies around the hole perimeter exhibited heterogeneity for holes produced with cutting clearances of 5.3% and 27.0%. This circumferential variation in cut edge shape arose from slight cutting misalignment, caused by the high strength of the material and the limited rigidity of the tool frame, which allowed minor flexing during the cutting process. Similar observations of non-coaxiality have been reported by Wang and Golovashchenko [51] and Stemler et al. [52], underscoring the challenging cutting conditions associated with punching AHSS sheets. Since sweeping of the two-dimensional cut edge results from PFEM model generated a homogeneous cut edge surface along the hole perimeter, an hybrid approach for obtaining realistic three-dimensional blank mesh was utilised in order to resemble the experimental hole surface. For the hole produced by 5.3% cutting clearance, islands of secondary burnish were obtained experimentally in an irregular manner around the hole perimeter. Fig. 12(a) shows a

Fig. 9. Experimental (black crosses) and numerical (blue boxes) results for cut edge characteristics across the full range of cutting clearances. Each graph illustrates the distribution of rollover, burnish, fracture, and burr respectively along the blank thickness, highlighting variations influenced by different cutting clearance.

Fig. 10. The transition from 2D PFEM cut edge contour to 2D FEM mesh and sweeping to 3D blank mesh for HET simulation.

panoramic image of the hole cut edge surface, where the intermediate blank/white surfaces shows the secondary burnish formation. To obtain a representative numerical mesh for HET simulation, experimental cut edge profiles constituted the cut edge shape of the circumferentially heterogeneous cut edge model. The residual results from the circumferentially homogeneous meshes were furthermore mapped to the numerical model, knowing that this assumption does not fully conform with the experimental residual state of the cut edge. Fig. 13 illustrates the hybrid pre-processing workflow, beginning with experimental cut edge contours obtained via 3D microscopy. These contours are then positioned in 3D space to construct the geometry of the sheared edge. The resulting geometry is subsequently discretised in a finite element pre-processor through a non-automated procedure. For the 5.3% cutting clearance case, the experimental area to be recreated by the hybrid modelling approach, spanning 90° of the hole perimeter from

Fig. 11. The axisymmetric cut edge results in (a) and the mapped and 45° circumferentially extruded 3D cut edge in (b) for 12.1% cutting clearance.

Fig. 12. Panoramic images of experimental cut edges in the left column and numerical 3D meshes of sheared edges in the right column for 5.3%, 12.1%, 27.0% and 40.3% cutting clearance.

−10° to 80° to the rolling direction. In a similar manner, the construction of the circumferentially heterogenous numerical cut edge perimeter for the 27% cutting clearance case is shown in Fig. 14.

4. Results and discussion

Experimentally, the sheared edge formability of the CP1000HD grade was examined by HER assessment and the edge cracking behaviour by microscopic studies of the fractured samples from the ISO 16630 tests. Comparing HER between varying cut edge conditions aimed to quantify the effect of sheared edge damage to cut edge formability under the ISO 16630 testing requirements. The detailed edge cracking analysis was performed to discern and isolate the edge cracking mechanisms with the aid of numerical modelling, giving in-going explanation of the edge cracking phenomenon.

Fig. 13. The workflow for creation of the 5.3% circumferentially heterogenous blank mesh for HET simulation. Starting with extracting 3D cut edge profiles using non-destructive 3D microscopy, to positioning and creation of CAD geometry. This is further discretised and the 3D blank mesh is created.

Fig. 14. Panoramic experimental cut edge with corresponding 3D cut edge profiles in (top) and the hybrid numerical 3D model in (bottom) for 27.0% cutting clearance.

4.1. Clearance dependent hole expansion ratio

The experimental HER values were determined according to the ISO 16630 standard and the results are shown in Fig. 15, also showing the variability of the experimental HER as error bars (standard deviation). The experimental results show a clear decline of

Fig. 15. Comparison of experimental and numerically predicted HER results. The numerical predictions include bars for circumferentially homogeneous cut edges for the entire range of cutting clearances, as well as heterogeneous cut edges at 5.3% and 27.0% cutting clearance.

HER from drilled edge conditions to edges from shear cutting, declaring a first order decrease of HER from undamaged to damaged edge condition. This observation is consistent with the literature and the common perception of sheared edge formability, as in the work by Konieczny and Henderson [1] Wang et al. [17] among others. The numerical modelling of drilled edge condition shows an accurate prediction of the HER, stating that the uniaxial failure strain level, determined by the method presented in Section 3.1, was feasible. By observing the HER of holes produced through shear cutting of different cutting clearances, it is apparent that the cut edges with large circumferential heterogeneity, as in the case of 5.3% and 27.0% cutting clearance, causes dramatically reduced HER. Meanwhile, more uniform cut edges caused less HER reduction compared to the undamaged cut edge. Comparing the results for 12.1% and 40.3% cutting clearance, the appearance of burr shown in Fig. 8 and the overall SAZ deformation imposed by the larger bending associated with 40.3% cutting clearance caused the reduction of HER. This behaviour was captured by the numerical modelling, suggesting that the axisymmetrical shape of the cut edge and residual results obtained from modelling were sufficient to describe the sheared edge damage relating to decline of HER.

An apparent modelling discrepancy is observed in Fig. 15 when comparing the use of circumferentially homogeneous and heterogeneous cut edge surface models for cutting clearances of 5.3% and 27.0%. When using the circumferentially homogeneous numerical blank meshes in Fig. 12, the modelled HER were clearly over-predicted for 5.3% and 27.0% cutting clearance. However, by including circumferential heterogeneities according to the hybrid models shown in Figs. 13 and 14, the predicted HER corresponds well to the experimental results. These results highlight the significant impact of circumferential heterogeneity on reducing the formability of sheared edges. Traditionally, research has focused on the *vertical* morphology of the cut edge, emphasising damage along the through-thickness direction of the blank. However, as shown in Fig. 15, it is equally important to consider the *horizontal* or circumferential cut edge morphology, as it appears to play a critical role in reducing sheared edge formability.

4.2. Edge cracking analysis

Examining the edge fracture pattern from ISO 16630 HET was done experimentally using a Keyence stereo 3D microscope (VHX-7000), enabling both 2D and 3D view of the edge crack. In addition to the predicted HER values, comparing the experimental and numerical fracture patterns was done to validate the numerical modelling for further use in investigating and explaining the clearance dependent edge cracking mechanisms.

As presented in Fig. 16(a) a single, 45° slanted, edge crack was detected during hole expansion testing of the drilled holes. A more magnified view of the experimental results in Fig. 16(b) shows small cracks at the extrusion punch side of the blank. These cracks were formed after the inner blank edge was plastically compressed in initial extrusion punch contact, followed by stretching during the hole expansion and constitutes the initiation of the edge crack. Fig. 16(b) also shows the effect of initial punch contact in terms of a deformed inner edge. The numerical modelling successfully replicated both the 45° through-thickness crack, as shown in Fig. 16(c), and the plastic deformation of the blank's inner edge. Additionally, it captured the formation of inner edge cracks with a similar pattern, as shown in Fig. 16(d). The final fracture then occurred due to the propagation of one of the inner edge cracks. These results highlight the implications of the ISO 16630 HET procedure, where the material experiences severe additional deformation at the blank inner edge due to mechanical contact with the expansion tool, leading to critical cracks along the perimeter. This suggests that the uniaxial tensile strength of the sheared edge is not primarily evaluated, as the cracks compromise the final HER results. This observation aligns with the findings of Kremaszky et al. [53], highlighting the critical influence of local damage and edge conditions on HER measurements, which often overshadow the material's inherent properties. According to the ISO 16630 standard, the test should be conducted on holes produced by 12±1% cutting clearance, thus a rollover formation will create a smoother contact

Fig. 16. In (a) the experimental top view of the drilled HET shows a slanted edge crack at $\approx 0^\circ$ to the rolling direction. In (b) the cracks at the inner blank edge and the compressive deformation of the edge is highlighted with $400 \times$ 3D microscopy. From numerical modelling of the drilled HET, (c) shows the slanted 45° crack at rolling direction and the inner edge fracture pattern due to the extrusion punch contact. In (d), the numerical damage parameter distribution is shown, highlighting the accumulated damage in the compressed blank inner edge which furthermore propagates and forms the through-thickness crack.

than for drilled edges. However, the strain hardening behaviour of the material will affect the rollover shape and consequently the extrusion punch contact.

In numerical modelling, the fracture initiated at a small offset from the rolling direction. For the experiment presented in Fig. 16, the crack occurred at a similar spot. However, in repeated experiments the crack could occur at the transverse to the rolling direction as well, indicating that the anisotropic fracture behaviour of the material was undistinguishable. This statement does however not hold for more anisotropic materials, as shown by Li et al. [19].

By observing the numerical damage and fracture evolution of the drilled HET in Fig. 17(a), it was seen that the through-thickness fracture propagated from the inner edge cracks towards the point where uniaxial tension caused local thinning of the edge. Fig. 17(b) also shows that the majority of both the outer edge (solid lines) and the inner edge (dotted lines) deforms in uniaxial tension. Thus, the knowledge of the uniaxial fracture strain remains an important parameter when determining the drilled edge formability, even though the inner edge plastic compression caused a notch-effect that accelerated the damage accumulation.

To further ensure the validity of the numerical HET modelling, the experimental and numerical punch force versus displacement results were compared. Fig. 18 show the corresponding results output, and the good correlation of the results further confirms that the constitutive modelling as well as the assumption of the friction coefficient is adequate.

Performing HET on specimens produced with 12% cutting clearances generated fracture patterns consisting of 45° slanted cracks, forming from both the burr side and from the interface between burnish and fracture, as seen in Fig. 19. Likewise, Matsuki et al. [54] observed fracture initiation at comparable sites in martensitic steel with a tensile strength of 980 MPa with a shear localisation behaviour similar to that of the CP1000HD grade. Given that the cut edge morphology was fairly homogenous around the hole perimeter, such fracture patterns were seen continuously. Comparing to numerical modelling results in Fig. 20, similar fracture patterns were seen across the numerical cut edge during ISO 16630 HET modelling.

Fig. 17. In (a), the distribution of the damage parameter D at the drilled edge during the last stages of the numerical HET. Here, the inner cracks and the thinning of the edge due to localised uniaxial strain forms the final fracture. In (b) the evolution of triaxiality η (black), lode angle parameter $\bar{\theta}$ (green) and damage parameter D (red) during the HET test for the drilled outer edge (solid lines) and the inner edge (dotted lines). The stages shown in (a) denoted A,B and C are plotted in (b) along the punch displacement axis.

Similar to the 12% cutting clearance case, 45° slanted cracks were seen for the 40% cutting clearance tests as well. However, the cracks were distinctively starting from the large burr formed during the shear cutting process, as shown in Fig. 21, most possibly at microscopic, sharp and uneven notches at the burr edge. Comparing to numerical modelling in Fig. 22, the fracture pattern was reproduced, but since no circumferential heterogeneities were present at the burr edge in the numerical modelling, the fracture initiations were less distinguishable. Instead, the numerically predicted HER value was mainly affected by the significant strain hardening imposed by the shear cutting process.

Considering the 5% cutting clearance case, the experimental cut edge surface was strongly heterogeneous in the hole perimeter, containing a mixture of secondary burnish surface islands and irregular fracture- and burnish surfaces as shown in Fig. 12(a). Due to this heterogeneity, several edge cracking modes were detected in experimental hole expansion tests. Fig. 23 shows in Pos. 1 splitting of secondary burnish surfaces, followed by shear band, in Pos. 2 cracks formed within uneven secondary burnish surface and in Pos. 3 at the lateral interface between fracture zone and secondary burnish. An effect of the shear band fracture was a lateral slip of the entire edge, promoting additional notches along the outer and inner blank edge. Multiple additional fracture patterns were detected in the experimental results, but the three highlighted in Fig. 23 were considered the most critical.

Comparing the numerical HET modelling results using the hybrid 5% clearance blank mesh in Fig. 24 to experiment showed several similarities. For instance, the lateral interface between secondary burnish islands and fracture surfaces acted as a fracture initiation site in numerical modelling (Fracture point 1). Also, splitting of secondary burnish was detected, triggered in the interface between primary fracture and top of the secondary burnish area (Fracture point 2). Such edge fracture was accelerated if the zone included circumferential heterogeneity. Additionally, the shear slip induced lateral movement of the blank edge was seen,

Fig. 18. Comparison between the experimental (black dashed) and numerical (blue) force response from drilled hole expansion testing.

Fig. 19. From the 12.1% cutting clearance case, edge cracks during HET were formed as 45° slanted cracks.

highlighted with the green dashed line in Fig. 24. With the well predicted HER value shown in Fig. 15 in mind, it appears that the circumferential heterogeneities introduced by the hybrid modelling technique were sufficiently realistic for predicting the edge fracture behaviour observed in experiment.

For 27.0% cutting clearance, the strong cut edge discontinuity at the partial burr interface acted as a distinct edge cracking trigger, as shown in Fig. 25. At the part of the cut edge perimeter with burr formation, a similar fracture pattern is seen as for the 40% cutting clearance case, whereas the no-burr section remain intact. In numerical modelling, the main crack was reproduced, but the secondary cracks from the burr was not, see Fig. 26.

By introducing circumferential heterogeneities by the hybrid modelling approach, both HER values and fracture patterns were adequately modelled. This suggests that variations in cut edge defects around the hole perimeter have a significant effect on edge cracking behaviour. Such defects, which may even occur in laboratory punching experiments due to cutting tool frame compliance as shown by Levin et al. [55], are likely to arise in industrial cutting processes as well. In industrial settings, higher dynamic loads can lead to similar instances of cutting misalignment, while common process anomalies such as uneven tool wear and edge chipping also can cause circumferential heterogeneities. This highlights the importance of constant cutting clearance along the sheared edge and that tool maintenance should be rigorous to minimise the risk irregular cut edge shape along the perimeter. The present study

Fig. 20. HET modelling of the 12.1% cutting clearance 3D mesh showed edge fracture to form as 45° slanted cracks from the burnish-to-fracture interface.

Fig. 21. The 40.3% cutting clearance HET showed slanted edge cracks growing from the massive burr.

Fig. 22. Numerical modelling of the 40.3% cutting clearance 3D mesh showed edge fracture to form as 45° slanted cracks from the burnish-to-fracture interface and in a single case from the burr.

Fig. 23. The 5.3% cutting clearance HET showed multiple edge cracking patterns due to the strong circumferential heterogeneity, where this image highlights the three most critical cracking modes.

Fig. 24. Numerical modelling of HET using the 5.3% hybrid 3D mesh showed distinct fracture patterns at the lateral interface at secondary burnish island (Fracture point 1) and splitting of secondary burnish surface (Fracture point 2).

focuses on sheared edge formability of holes, thus emphasising the importance of circumferential homogeneity for increased HER. The statements are expected to hold for open-cut configurations as well, where the uniformity of the horizontal shape of the cut edge then is considered critical.

Studying the numerical stress state at fracture for the different HET cases aided the understanding of the edge fracture mechanisms. Fig. 27(a) shows the evolution of the damage parameter D at the fracture point in $\eta, \bar{\theta}$ -space for the respective HET case, whereas Fig. 27(b) shows the corresponding stress state at failure. Here it was seen that the drilled specimen outer edge deforms and fails in pure uniaxial tension, consistent to the work by Butcher et al. [56], whereas the inner edge deformation is less consistent due to the inner edge cracks. The HET simulations results of blanks from 12% and 40% cutting clearance also showed cut edge deformation and failure at uniaxial tension. Consequently, the varying levels of plastic pre-damage were identified as the primary factor reducing the computed HER values. For the circumferentially heterogeneous cut edge cases, blanks from 5% and 27% cutting clearance, the deformation and failure were shifted to higher triaxialities with complex and varying stress states. This partially explains the reduced HER values from these simulations, in combination with the stress concentrations at the circumferential imperfections.

Fig. 28 presents the fringe plot of the damage parameter D , illustrating its evolution from the initial post-shear cutting state through the intermediate HET stage to the final edge fracture for 12.1% and 27.0% cutting clearance case. This visualisation highlights how pre-damage from shear cutting progresses during edge forming and ultimately leads to failure. It is evident that damage accumulation increases substantially for the circumferentially homogeneous cut edges produced with 12.1% and 40.3% cutting clearances, whereas this accumulation is less pronounced for the heterogeneous cut edges resulting from 5.3% and 27.0% cutting clearances. The damage evolution is visualised for the 5.3% and 40.3% cutting clearance cases in Fig. A.30.

Fig. 25. HET experiments with 27.0% cutting clearance showed distinct edge cracking at the burr/no-burr interface.

Fig. 26. Similarly to the HET experiments, numerical HET with hybrid 27.0% cutting clearance mesh showed that burr/no-burr interface initiated edge fracture.

4.3. Residual SAZ pre-damage

To examine the effects of pre-damage on sheared edge formability, numerical modelling of the presented HET cases was conducted without residual results mapping. As described in Section 3.3, this mapping includes the stress and strain tensors, equivalent plastic strain, von Mises stress, and damage parameters. Comparing the numerically obtained HER, with and without the inclusion of mapped pre-damage, to the drilled HET results highlights the influence of circumferential heterogeneities. Strong heterogeneities, such as those observed at 5% and 27% cutting clearance, remain the primary factor driving HER reduction compared to undamaged conditions. Removing the pre-damage in these cases had a percentually large impact on the HER (50% and 47% increase respectively), but the edge formability remained poor compared to undamaged conditions.

In contrast, circumferentially homogeneous cut edges at 12% and 40% cutting clearance showed notable differences in numerical HER improvements after omitting pre-damage mapping. Specifically, the HER increased by 30% for the 12% clearance case, compared to a much larger increase of 103% for the 40% clearance case. This significant difference highlights the crucial role of SAZ pre-damage in reducing edge formability.

The smaller improvement in the 12% cutting clearance case suggests that the extent of plastic straining and SAZ damage in this scenario is relatively limited, resulting in a lesser impact from the removal of pre-damage. Conversely, the 40% clearance case, characterised by substantial plastic deformation and more severe SAZ damage, demonstrated a much stronger dependency on pre-damage removal to enhance edge formability. These results underline the importance of understanding the interplay between cutting clearance, SAZ pre-damage, and the resulting effects on sheared edge formability. In the case of 40% cutting clearance, the large rollover formation also contributed to a smoother extrusion punch contact than in drilled conditions which reduced the

Fig. 27. In (a) the evolution of the damage parameter D in η , $\bar{\theta}$ -space at fracture initiation points for the different clearances (Cl.) is shown and in (b) the corresponding final stress state at fracture is marked in η , $\bar{\theta}$ -space.

amount of damage imposed by the initial contact. The numerically obtained HER values, with and without mapped pre-damage results are shown in Fig. 29 along with the experimental HER values.

4.4. Modelling limitations

In this study, many of the circumferential imperfections found around the cut edge perimeter were on microscopic scale and therefore not possible to account for in numerical modelling. Such micro-defects were not represented by the plastic strain driven damage- and failure modelling as they did not originate from void growth and coalescence. The notches and micro-cracks instead originated from the microscopic-scale roughness of the cut edge, a statement further reinforced by the recent findings of Matsuki et al. [54]. A possible way to deal with this in modelling could be to consider fracture mechanics approaches. Experimentally, fracture mechanics expressed as the essential work of fracture is a suitable measure for understanding edge cracking resistance, as shown by Frómata et al. [57]. The material's apparent susceptibility to notches and micro-cracks observed in the present study further supports the use of such fracture mechanics approaches both for experimental edge cracking assessment and in numerical failure modelling. A similar study to the one just presented could also be applied to related AHSS issues, such as reduced fatigue life of sheared edges or hydrogen embrittlement. It is plausible that the material's notch sensitivity may play a significant role in these phenomena as well.

5. Conclusions

This article addresses some critical aspects of high strength complex-phase stretch-flangeability that provides important insights to the edge cracking problem. By observing the edge cracking mechanisms from ISO 16630 tests with varying clearance and extended numerical analysis, following conclusions were drawn:

- Circumferential heterogeneities at the cut edge shifted the deformation and failure mode into a more pronounced tensile state which accelerated the edge cracking. In combination with notch effects from the cut edge irregularities, the sheared edge formability was drastically decreased.

Fig. 28. Fringe plot of the damage parameter D , illustrating its progression from the initial post-shear cutting state through the intermediate HET stage to the final edge fracture for the 12.1% and 27.0% cutting clearance cases. The plot highlights how pre-damage from shear cutting evolves during edge forming, ultimately leading to failure.

- The decline of sheared edge formability from the circumferential heterogeneity outranked the negative effect of through-thickness pre-damage of the SAZ.
- When the cut edge shape was homogenous in the circumferential direction, the pre-damage from the shear cutting was the main damaging effect causing reduced stretch-flangeability. This suggests that axisymmetric shear cutting models are effective for predicting SAZ damage and assess sheared edge formability when clearance and cut edge morphology are uniform around the hole perimeter.
- The numerical framework, based on shear cutting simulations using PFEM, enabled the assessment of sheared edge formability and predicted the edge cracking to a large extent. However, due to the continuum-based modelling approach, the simulations did not fully capture the exact cracking behaviour of micromechanical notches.
- Some circumferential imperfections at the cut edge, being microscopic in scale, were not captured by strain-driven damage models, as they originated from cut edge roughness rather than void coalescence. Incorporating fracture mechanics approaches into both experimental and numerical frameworks may therefore improve the understanding and prediction of edge cracking resistance in AHSS.
- This study highlights the importance of maintaining consistent tool alignment, cutting clearance, and edge quality in industrial processes. The sensitivity to circumferential heterogeneities and micro-notches underscores the need for strict control of cutting conditions to improve the reliability of AHSS cold-forming.

Fig. 29. Numerically predicted HER results obtained with and without mapped residual pre-damage from the shear cutting process.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Olle Sandin: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Patrick Larour:** Validation, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Samuel Hammarberg:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jörgen Kajberg:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Daniel Casellas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Patrick Larour reports a relationship with voestalpine Stahl GmbH that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. Damage evolution in het modelling

As presented in Section 4.2, the damage evolution throughout HET modelling for cutting clearance cases 5.3% and 40.3% is given in Fig. A.30.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Fig. A.30. Fringe plot of the damage parameter D , illustrating its progression from the initial post-shear cutting state through the intermediate HET stage to the final edge fracture for the 5.3% and 40.3% cutting clearance cases. The plot highlights how pre-damage from shear cutting evolves during edge forming, ultimately leading to failure.

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